

AN ANALYSIS SEMIOTIC IN MUSIC VIDEO OF “CALL ME BY YOUR NAME” BY LIL NAS X

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to analyze the meaning of signs found in the music video "Call Me by Your Name" by Lil Nas X (2021). The research method applied in this study is a qualitative descriptive approach consistent with identifying and analyzing some observations through the music video. This study analyzes the meaning of signs found in the music video "Call Me by Your Name" by Lil Nas X (2021). The research method applied in this study is a qualitative descriptive approach consistent with identifying and analyzing some observations through the music video. This study uses semiotic by Barthes's (1977) theory to discover and analyze. The result showed that from an official youtube account, namely "Lil Nas X." This study found that 35 signs have the meaning implied by Lil Nas X to show the song lyrics and pictures that describe the denotations and connotations about LGBT and Satanists.

Keywords: Barthes' Theory, Lil Nas X, LGBT, Satanist And Semiotics Signs..

INTRODUCTION

Microlinguistics is more suitable for language study, while Macrolinguistics focuses on the inter-language field, mainly including context. According to Mahmood (2017) states that "the main tool or unit of research in pragmatics is culture, mind, brain, and so on, rather than phoneme, morpheme, and sentence" from this statement, Macrolinguistics is a scope of linguistics that studies language concerning the world outside language, which is the language that is related to psychology, sociology, communication, and forensics. Microlinguistics is a study of linguistics whose application is related to the language of our daily lives, including the field of pure language scientific linguistics, especially semiotic.

Semiotics is a study of signs are made and how the signs can be accepted and realized in everyday life. This study discusses how to create meaning and awareness derived from visual culture and structure. Onursoy (2015) it has a meaning that semiotics makes its meaning which has a symbol from the time the communication was created. According to Crick & Grushka (2009) as cited in Crick (2006) states that semiotic systems, and the image of symbols is a significant metaphor. This statement explains that each system has a strong relationship between symbols and semiotic systems. Sign in the semiotics that we encounter almost every day realizes that this type of sign in every human being can be informative interpreted meanings. The semiotics of sign communication can emphasize the production of signs. Mudjiyanto & Nur (2013) the sign is describes as a symbol that juxtaposes a reference source with a mutual agreement in a cultural element.

Therefore, many signs that change the brand image means are implemented and applied continuously, Combe et al. (2003) from the statement that symbols must be culturally studied, these traits have identical knowledge and values, but symbols can In addition be found in illustrated media, with current technological advances and the development of social media, which is very rapid. Significant symbols can In addition be found in technology such as advertisements, song lyrics, videos, and music videos to

support technology. Furthermore, According to Young (1996) as cited in Wahab et al. (2012) says that technology has results that solve human needs in acquiring knowledge. From this statement, we can conclude that humans need technology to quickly and easily solve a problem of their need.

Moreover, most technologies change the way people work by improving performance Crick & Grushka (2009). It can describe that the relationship between semiotics and technology has a very close relation where technological progress contains many symbols that have meaning. Fedorov (2015) in addition says, "Media technologies: creation (supported by modern computer technology, for example, PowerPoint) of media projects associated with the sign system of media texts." one of the technologies often found in several networks is a comprehensive development technology called social media.

Music Video Call Me by Your Name is a song released on March 26, 2021, through Columbia records. Written by Lil Nas X, and was awarded the MTV Millennial Awards, Global Hit Awards of the year in 2021, then his music got number 01 Billboard hot 100. On the other hand this music video also trending in a social media which is YouTube and TikTok with more than 200 billion views in a week. The phenomenon occurs in a community, namely the LGBT community, which is a group that represents a gay community, "Lesbian, gay, bisexual, and transgender", that communities who like each other of the same sex. The Satanist community consists of satanic worshipers who use satanic symbols such as the Baphomet symbol or the goat's head. The community of an Illuminati is to replace Christianity with a religion of reason or a much closed secret fraternity. The community is implemented in this music video by bringing relation signs of LGBT, Satanist, and Illuminati.

Based on the problems above, the writer analyses music entitled "Lil Nas X Call Me By Your Name" where the song contains many sentences that have figurative meanings in a lyric, Furthermore that there are many symbols in the music video "Lil Nas X Call Me By Your Name" which has many elements such as the influence of LGBT, Illuminati, and Satanists, and many other symbols are found in the music video. Such things are interesting to study.

There are two statements of the problem regarding this study, (1) what icons, indexes, or symbols are shown in the "Call Me by Your Name" by Lil Nas X? and (2) what are the semiotic signs found in the music video of "Call Me by Your Name" by Lil Nas X with Barthes' (1977) theory? As the result, this study is conducted to (1) to identify, indexes, or symbols are shown in the "Call Me by Your Name" by Lil Nas X. and (2) to identify the semiotic signs in the music video of "Call Me by Your Name" by Lil Nas X with Barthes' (1977) theory. to analyze semiotics in music video, the writer chose the theory of Barthes (1977) who created two semiotic systems that focus on icons, indexes, or symbols are shown and the semiotic signs found in the music video "Call Me By Your Name" by Lil Nas X.

METHOD

In conducting this study, the writer analyzed the meaning of the symbols contained in the music video. The writer used the theory of Barthes. Furthermore, the writer will use a qualitative approach that method entails employing data collection techniques based on the meaning and observations of an analysis data. As Howard (2012) cited in Chandler (2002) explains that "Describe qualitative study in terms of meanings, concepts, definitions, metaphors, symbols, and descriptions of things."

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Findings

The data finding consists of 35 data findings that tell the signs in the "Call Me by Your Name" Music video was taken based on their scenes, such as; non-verbal and verbal, including written lyrics, type of shot, and denotation connotation meaning.

Analysis

After finding the data, the writer need to analyze the meaning of the denotation and connotation in the music video by Lil Nas X entitled Call me by Your Name with Barthe's theory. The following is an analysis of some of the data found:

Datum: 1

Figure 1 - (The view of sky and clouds)

Denotation meaning:

This scene represents a pretty colourful cloud with a dominant purple colour and a little dark colour. It is decorated with a luminous space in the middle. Afterwards, there is a cloud shaped like a horn as a barrier to space. Moreover, this scene uses medium-long shots.

Connotation meaning:

The connotation are shows the view of sky and clouds [00:02] how the condition of the sky describes the breadth of hope. The images are created colourful as if to convey the beauty of that hope. Furthermore, behind this hope, the colours are similar to LGBT's flag as it shows the meaning of the flag itself where their gender is enshrined with various colours or rainbow symbols. Additionally, behind these colours, clouds are sketched, which are quite dark in colour to indicate that there is still a void behind the beautiful colours and hopes that they have built. Hence, the image of the bright room is meant to create a new place for LGBT people to reach their dreams. However, the horn symbol depicted by the cloud before the room lit up seemed to signal the consequences they would have to accept when stepping into the sphere of light. So, the meaning of "In Life" is that the life LGBT people want to build in achieving their hopes even though they are against real life. The camera uses a medium-long shots to show the beauty created from clouds with colourful bases. The song's of the lyrics is "In Life".

Datum: 2

Figure 2 – (The scenery of abandoned building)

Denotation meaning:

The denotation of this scene is a winding river with some abandoned buildings, and some of them have collapsed. In addition, the colour is dominated by purple as the primary colour of the sky coupled with gray fog. This picture In addition shows a statue of

a man's face. Afterwards some flowers grow on the red soil, and the song's lyrics related to this scene is "We lock them away" with an extreme long shot.

Connotation meaning:

The scenery are shown of abandoned building [00:09]. It has many meanings. The first meaning is found in a winding river where the water there depicts a previous life. The picture of a winding river indicates that life is full of obstacles and is not easy to navigate. Secondly, several abandoned buildings as a sign that the past was indeed created, but its time has been destroyed. The building seems to relate to the image of a building resulting from Roman architecture, namely the Roman Forum, where the roman forum is an ancient Roman government building surrounded by crumbling buildings.

Thirdly, the purple colour indicates hidden aspirations or information such as nobility, mystery, ambition, magic, self-esteem, and spirituality. The grey colour of the clouds has a dark or gloomy meaning. Hence, in conveying the meaning here, behind the bright purple colour and seems to have much hope, there is a dark story that might fade the brightness. In this scene, the statue of a man's face seems to represent his fellow tribesmen for the wishes or characteristics that want to be revived. The statues and crumbling buildings seem to hark back to the time of Prophet Luth AS, who is believed to be the story for Muslims. There is a place of punishment for LGBT people or same-sex lovers deviating from the actual teachings. It says that all these people were punished for becoming statues and destroyed the deviant life that had been built there so that they seemed to want to mention this incident as a dark history that wanted to be coloured again by the people who seemed to come back to life and the statue was marked as part of them.

Event though, in this scene, flowers growing on red soil are In addition depicted as a message that even without a touch of green there, life can still be saved with flowers as a symbol of life full of beauty that can still be maintained. "We lock them away" shows that the past, which was full of blasphemy, opposition, and prohibitions, was indeed felt by their people, so resentment grew there. An extreme long shot is uses in this scene to identify the surrounding environment and explain a culture value from an abandoned buildings.

Datum: 3

Figure 3 – (The Eden garden view)

Denotation meaning:

The denotation in this it seems like Gharqad Tree or Lycium (Box-thorns). In addition this scene shown how the situation resembles the Garden of Eden. In addition, it shows a stone resembling a hand lying on the ground. Whereas, a river has the beauty of its surroundings. The lyrics of the song "We Don't" and the camera uses extreme long shot.

Connotation meaning:

The pictures in datum three was taken in [00:15] is the Erden garden view. It proven with the several signs that contained in this scene. Significantly, there is a sign that resembles the Gharqad Tree or Lycium (Box-thorns) as known as as a Dajjal's tree where

the people who follow Dajjal will get protection at the end of time by the tree. It is located in the most beautiful gardens referred to in the Bible as the Garden of Eden. That is, looks like to explain about the pleasures and happiness of heaven are there. According to bible there is the most beautiful it is Garden of Eden (Genesis 2:20-23) and (Genesis 2:4b - 3:24) explains that it is a tree of life that knows the side of good and bad. Besides, there is the shape of a hand lying on the ground as if it has a meaning that there is a place of hope come. A river that has a shadow of its surrounding environment is a river that gives life to the environment as if the shadow is part of the result of the river's flow that is deliberately displayed in the scene.

Moreover, according to the Qur'an (Al- Araf 24-25), the Garden of Eden is the place where Adam and Hawa got the first temptation has given by the Devil. The temptation is to eat a delicious fruit called Khuldi. Whereas, the Khuldi tree is a symbol of the first sin committed by the first human. The lyrics of the song in this scene is "We Don't". It refers to the hint that they will not do anything beyond the limits of the favors given. Furthermore, the camera shot uses is extreme long shot to shown the whole atmosphere of the Eden garden and river to shows a beauty of a life.

Datum: 4

Figure 4 – (The stalking snake)

Denotation meaning:

This scene shows a snake with scales snake colour combination which are black and gold. Furthermore, this scene In addition shows it crawling besides the stones. The place in this scene has a blue background with red combination colour. Afterwards, taking pictures on this screen using close-up shots and "Welcome to Montero" contained in the song's lyrics.

Connotation meaning:

The scene in datum four captured in [00:17] is about the gold and black scaly snake. Meanwhile, gold has a power of splendour, and black has a meaning of gloom as a sign to indicate the snake's characteristic in this scene, depending on how humans understand him.

The philosophy of snakes is that they find their prey, they will approach it slowly, even with a stabbed signal if the prey resists. In addition, some rocks illustrate how the snake aims at something slowly and carefully by hiding behind one of the large stones. Otherwise, there is blue soil with bluegrass decorations and a mixture of red, hot and cold were created at the same time. Therefore, the snake's nature and temptations are discussed here.

Furthermore, the song's lyrics in the scene are "Welcome to Montero," which implies that the snake wishes to invite someone to join with his group. The camera uses close-up shot that focuses to the snake and to demonstrate their physical characteristics that snake is a part of Dajjal's community.

Datum: 5

Figure 5 – (A man who relaxing under the tree)

Denotation meaning:

This scene shows a man relaxing under the shade of the khuldi tree, as known as the omniscient tree of life, where Adam and Eve were first united. Like wise, the man took a long shot while playing a pink guitar with the song's lyrics in the scene is "I caught it bad yesterday" it uses long shot.

Connotation meaning:

The connotation are in datum five was taken in [00:20], which means a man sitting under the khuldi tree where Adam and Eve grew up. However, no woman is created in this scene to grow up with the man. It indicates that man are not always required to be in pairs with man, women, and vice versa.

Even though, the man plays his pink guitar to entertain himself in silence through the strains of a guitar, which has an elegant pink colour, this scene was created using the lyrics of the song " I caught it bad yesterday," which has an implied message that the man's mindset on his partner, which a woman required, had been removed dismissed with the word "Caught it bad" as part of the strength of his belief in something that he had previously been unable to agree with it. The shoot technique in this scene is a long shot as of support for the the male body language and the surrounding environment especially a khuldi tree.

Datum: 6

Figure 6 – (The appearance of a man with a snake on the tree)

Denotation meaning:

The denotation in this scene there is a snake wrapped around the trunk with the appearance of a man relaxing under the tree, with the song's lyrics, "You hit me with a call to your place" The camera uses long shot.

Connotation meaning:

The connotation are in datum six was taken in [00:26] like a snake demon attempting to approach and trick that man. The snake wrapped around his body as a sign that he should try to wrap his goal around the target. This scene depicts how a man's sinful flow was created. "You hit me with a call to your place" the song's lyrics implied a special call to the man to being a part of snake demon. The camera uses a long shot depicts the two objects between a man and a snake's body with the situation of Eden garden view.

Datum: 7

Figure 7 – (A human with a snake body)

Denotation meaning:

In this scene, there is a snake demon stalking someone from behind a tree trunk. In addition, there is a symbol of the eye of the Antichrist on the forehead of the snake demon. On the other hand, a pink magic flicker appears near the snake's body. Furthermore, the song's lyrics in this scene is "Ain't been out in a while anyway" The camera shot uses a full shot.

Connotation meaning:

The connotation is identified as pictured in [00:28]. This scene is snake stealth with its position stalking someone, the snake appears to be observing his target to become his prey. The snake demon is afterwards discovered to have Dajjal's eyes on his forehead, indicating that he is a member of Dajjal's people.

However, this scene creates the impression that the snake invites its prey to join the Dajjal community like him. The pink glitter that appears from the side of his body indicates the magic power that he possesses to deceive him. Pink is regarded as a graceful colour as if it wishes to take a woman's place to catch its prey. The song's lyrics that appear in this scene are "Ain't been out in a while anyway" It is implied message that there will be a desire to re-form sin in its place of the tree, which is described as the first sin tree for humans. Full shot shooting is to find out the whole body of the snake demon and his expression.

Datum: 8

Figure 8 – (A view of demon snake / Naagin)

Denotation meaning:

In this scene, the snake demon is stalking the man who is relaxing under the tree. The camera uses an over the shoulder shot, the lyrics of the song "Was hoping I could catch you throwing smiles in my face".

Connotation meaning:

The connotation in datum eight was taken in [00:30] this scene is method of the snake demon to stalking the human who is under the tree. The snake is looking for a man who appears to be daydreaming. Besides that, this snake demon represents how the devil tries to seduce or trick humans. This is because many people believe that empty souls are easily duped by the devil. The song's lyrics "Was hoping I could catch you throwing smiles in my face" convey the meaning that the snake demon really wants to catch him as part of his devilish passion. The shot taken in this scene is an over the shoulder shot to show how a snake demon stalks its prey stealthily and also to show part of his body's.

Datum: 9

Figure 9 – (A man who resembles a tree)

Denotation meaning:

The denotation of this scene is a tree with a shape of a human looking at the camera. He has a symbol of the eye on his forehead. In this scene, the song's lyrics are "You're cute enough to fuck with me tonight", with uses a medium close-up shot.

Connotation meaning:

The connotation in datum nine was taken in [00:36] is about a human who resembles the tree where his hair is depicted with twigs and leaves. The man has Dajjal's eyes on his forehead, as if he is be a part of Dajjal. The eye of that kind of human has a meaning called "The Eye of Providence" or the eye of God, commonly called the Illuminati. Illuminati is an organization or group, both real and fictitious, that believes in the existence of spirits.

Furthermore, the song's lyrics in this scene are "You're cute enough to fuck with me tonight" which implies the message about the invitation to make a relationship with the stealth to be a part of the Dajjal community. It seems to give a sign that humans can be plunged into sin for the pleasure of the devil's seduction. The human face that looks at the camera is intended to give a sense of welcome to humans who will become a new part of their people. The camera shot uses is a medium close-up to show the expression of the tree man in welcoming a new guest to be his part.

Datum: 10

Figure 10 – (A man who resembles a flower)

Denotation meaning:

The denotation in this scene are flowers that resemble humans. The flower has ahead in the center of the petals with a protruding tongue, the Dajjal's eyes on his forehead, and a seductive gaze. Otherwise, camera uses in this scene is close-up shot, the song's lyrics are "Looking at the table and I see the reason".

Connotation meaning:

The connotation in this scene was taken in [00:38] is a human's head in the middle of a flower petal which describes the demon. The demon has the symbol of the Dajjal's eye on his forehead as part of the Dajjal's followers. Afterwards, the demon sticks out his tongue with a seductive gaze or is tempted by something so that it seems like he wants to eat it. In this scene, the song's lyrics are "Looking at the table and I see the reason". It has a sign about the readiness of the demons to tempt their new followers and believe that humans will be ensnared by their temptations. The camera shot made in this scene is a close-up shot to show the expression of his face that to instigate a people to having a sex.

Datum: 11

Figure 11 – (The clouds with the shape of a human face)

Denotation meaning:

The denotation in this scene is the presence of a cloud in the shape of a human face. Otherwise, it has a combination of purple and a little mixture of galaxy colours. In addition, there is a storm that was created in the cloud. The song lyrics that describe this scene are “Baby, you live the life, but nigga, you ain’t livin” the camera shot was taken in this scene is the full shot.

Connotation meaning:

The connotations in this scene, which was taken in [00:42], are clouds depicted with faces like a human. They were spies who could see the life beneath from all sides. The clouds are purple with a mixture of galaxy colours, representing how the sky illustrates the contributions of some rainbow colour, a symbol of LGBT.

Furthermore, the base colour of the sky is blue, and the colour of the galaxy supports their lives. The song's lyrics in this scene is "Baby, you living the life, but nigga, you ain't livin," which means that the lyrics are dedicated to a part of them where the word "Nigga" itself is black people, which comes from the word "Nigger." For black people, the word has a negative connotation. In addition, because the word is too sensitive, it should only be used by those people (Black People). It appears to imply the existence of racism, which they perceive as one of the oppressions they are unable to resist. These lyrics refer to the black people or “Niggas” who do not deserve to live correctly and pursue their dreams and hopes. Therefore, the irony in this figure of speech is expected to change people's perceptions of black people. This scene uses a full shot to focus on the overall shape of the clouds and a colours of the clouds.

Datum: 12

Figure 12 – (The scenery of a snake chasing a man)

Denotation meaning:

The denotation in this scene describes a snake demon was chasing a man. It happens when the man sees the snake demon form about to stab him, terrified and shocked. In addition, the song's lyrics in this scene are "Cocaine," with the camera shot being a long shot.

Connotation meaning:

The connotation in this scene, which was captured in [00:43], depicts a snake demon chasing a man as if the demon was about to stab its prey to make the man a part of his life. However, the man was aware of that situation and tried to flee the demon with panic and surprise. The song's lyrics in this scene is "Cocaine" it can be implied the causes of addiction. Therefore, the snake demon wants to lure the man into his trap and intends to

drug men with his addictive temptation. Afterwards, a camera shot in this scene is long to show and explain the two characters' expressions in one frame.

CONCLUSIONS

This chapter deals with the conclusions and suggestions. These are based on the analysis semiotic of music video that Lil Nas X wants to deliver through the “Call Me by Your Name” and its surroundings which are stated as follows:

Conclusions

Based on the analysis in the previous chapter, icons, indexes, or symbols in the "Call Me by Your Name" by Lil Nas X music video were found by the writer related to the theory of Barthes (1977). The datum was found in this study are 35 signs and it concluded that “Call me by your name” contain the signs of LGBT and satanist Illuminati worshippers. This music video was introduced by a man named Lil Nas X who is the main character in this video has a relationship with the same gender and a devil. Every scene in this video shows an LGBT such as a rainbow symbol that symbolizes of LGBT’s flag, scene sexuality with the same gender by Lil Nas X, a man was sitting alone under the tree of an Eden garden which means that there are no couples in his life because sometimes he can be a woman and a man. Then the next scenes depict Plato's literary statement on the tree trunk explains the support for LGBT behavior regarding someone who has two personalities in one body, a man wearing a pink dress is an illustration of a woman, for instance, Lil Nas X wearing a wig and a necklace in his neck, it is a representation of a woman but in man’s character (LGBT).

Afterward, the video also shows several signs of illumination, for instance, a snake with an eye on his forehead, the tree with a human body, a cloud with a shape of a human face, snake with a human body that explains to be a part of Illuminati or Dajjal’s community. The kingdom of the devil with red lava, a horn of goat’s head, a symbol of a pyramid, and a symbol of a pentagram with the quotes inside “Damnant quod non-intelligent” is to shows about the religion of Illuminati and satanist, in the video, Lil Nas X describing his belief in Satan. The message implied in this music video that Lil Nas X wants to deliver through the “Call Me by Your Name” music video is that to respect another gender, especially LGBT, choose a good environment, filter first before having information, and belief with one and only god.

Suggestions

Based on the analysis in the previous chapters, The writer suggests for the students of English Department who are interested in semiotic analysis can be more understanding of an object with support by related studies, reading a theory book by an expert for instance, Ferdinand de Saussure, Charles Sanders Peirce, and Roland Barthes, also supported by some journals related to the topic. Furthermore, it would be better to deeply analyze in another object of semiotics with the expert theory.

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